

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA):IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

A Comprehensive Review Of Quercetin-Containing Plant Leaves And Their Impact On Hyperlipidemia

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 23 Aug 2024

Accepted: 27 Aug 2024

Published: 31 Aug 2024

Keywords:

Quercetin, Lipid Metabolism, Plant Leaves, Antihyperlipidemic Activity, And Cardiovascular Health.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13623665

ABSTRACT

Elevated blood lipid levels, or hyperlipidemia, are a major risk factor for cardiovascular diseases. This review emphasizes the role of plant leaves in lipid regulation by offering a thorough analysis of the antihyperlipidemic potential of over 100 different plant leaves. The review specifically calls attention to the role of the flavonoid quercetin, which is well-known for its ability to modulate lipid levels. We evaluate the efficacy of a broad variety of plant leaves in reducing levels of cholesterol and triglycerides by looking at mechanisms like antioxidant activity, anti-inflammatory effects, and modification of lipid metabolism pathways. These plant leaves provide a variety of bioactive compounds with notable antihyperlipidemic effects, which are frequently amplified by the presence of quercetin, according to data from preclinical and clinical studies [1, 2, 3]. Quercetin's potential synergy with plant-derived interventions is illustrated by a detailed discussion of its role in improving lipid profiles, inhibiting lipid peroxidation, and enhancing endothelial function. [4,5,6] This review summarizes the results of recent studies, highlights the potential of quercetin and plant leaves in the management of hyperlipidemia, and suggests directions for further investigation to fully grasp the combined therapeutic potential of these compounds.

INTRODUCTION

A significant risk factor for the onset of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) like atherosclerosis, coronary artery disease, and stroke is hyperlipidemia, which is defined by elevated blood lipid levels [1]. Although statins and fibrates, two common pharmaceutical treatments

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

for hyperlipidemia, have demonstrated efficacy, they are frequently accompanied by side effects and restrictions [2]. As a result, natural treatments especially those based on plants are gaining popularity as complementary or alternative approaches to treating lipid disorders [3]. Research has been done on the possible antihyperlipidemic effects of many plant leaves. Numerous bioactive substances found in the leaves of these plants have been shown to regulate lipid metabolism, lower cholesterol, and enhance general cardiovascular health [4]. Of these bioactive substances, the flavonoid quercetin, which is extensively found in plants, has received a lot of attention due to its ability to lower cholesterol. The mechanisms of action of quercetin include its capacity to modulate important enzymes involved in lipid metabolism and its antioxidant qualities, which reduce oxidative stress [5][6]. The effectiveness of quercetin and other plant-derived compounds in lowering lipid levels and enhancing lipid profiles has been demonstrated by recent research. For instance, studies have demonstrated that quercetin can raise levels of high-density lipoprotein (HDL) and considerably reduce serum triglycerides and total cholesterol [7, 8]. These advantages might be increased by quercetin's synergistic interactions with other phytochemicals found in plant leaves [9]. In spite of encouraging outcomes, a thorough analysis that synthesizes information from numerous studies is required to fully comprehend the potential of these natural interventions and their modes of action. This review aims to evaluate the antihyperlipidemic activity of over 100 plant leaves, with a specific focus on quercetin. By synthesizing current research, we seek to provide insights into the efficacy of these plant-based approaches and identify areas for future research.

QUERCETIN

One naturally occurring flavonoid that can be found in grains, fruits, and vegetables is quercetin,

which has shown promising results in the treatment of hyperlipidemia. Elevated blood lipid levels, or hyperlipidemia, represent a substantial risk factor for cardiovascular illnesses. The main ways that quercetin lowers cholesterol are via its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant characteristics. It assists in lowering inflammation and oxidative stress, both of which are strongly associated with problems with lipid metabolism. [5,6] Research indicates that quercetin can raise HDL cholesterol while lowering LDL, total, and triglyceride levels. The improvement of cardiovascular health is facilitated by this modification of lipid profiles. The augmentation of lipid catabolism and inhibition of cholesterol synthesis are the mechanisms underlying these effects. To bolster its role in managing hyperlipidemia, quercetin may also affect the expression of genes linked to lipid metabolism. [7,8] Notwithstanding these encouraging findings, more thorough and extensive research is still needed to fully understand the clinical efficacy of quercetin in hyperlipidemia, confirm its advantages, and determine the proper dosage. However, more research is necessary to fully explore its potential as a supplemental therapeutic agent for the management of hyperlipidemia. [9]

QUERCETIN-RICH PLANT FAMILIES

Strong flavonoid quercetin is well known for having anti-inflammatory and antioxidant qualities. It contributes to the health benefits of various plants by being present in significant concentrations in their leaves. Plants with high quercetin content are frequently studied for their ability to control lipid levels, lower inflammation, and promote cardiovascular health. The inclusion of sources rich in quercetin in diets can lead to better health outcomes, as the presence of quercetin in these plants emphasizes their significance in nutrition and therapeutic applications. [10,11]

1. LILIACEAE (LILY FAMILY) [12]

- a. Onion (*Allium cepa*)
- b. Garlic (*Allium sativum*)
- c. Leek (*Allium ampeloprasum*)
- d. Chives (*Allium schoenoprasum*)
- 2. POLYGONACEAE (BUCKWHEAT FAMILY) [13]**
 - a. Buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum*)
 - b. Rhubarb (*Rheum rhabarbarum*)
- 3. FABACEAE (LEGUME FAMILY) [14]**
 - a. Red Clover (*Trifolium pratense*)
 - b. Soybean (*Glycine max*)
 - c. Green Bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*)
 - d. Pea (*Pisum sativum*)
- 4. RUTACEAE (RUE FAMILY) [15]**
 - a. Rue (*Ruta graveolens*)
 - b. Citrus Fruits (e.g., Orange - *Citrus sinensis*, Lemon - *Citrus limon*)
- 5. LAMIACEAE (MINT FAMILY) [16]**
 - a. Mint (*Mentha spp.*)
 - b. Sage (*Salvia officinalis*)
 - c. Thyme (*Thymus vulgaris*)
 - d. Oregano (*Origanum vulgare*)
- 6. DIOSCOREACEAE (YAM FAMILY) [17]**
 - a. Yam (*Dioscorea spp*)
 - b. Chinese Yam (*Dioscorea opposita*)
- 7. APIACEAE (CARROT FAMILY) [18]**
 - a. Parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*) -.
 - b. Celery (*Apium graveolens*) -.
 - c. Carrot (*Daucus carota*)
- 8. ASTERACEAE (ASTER FAMILY) [19]**
 - a. Artichoke (*Cynara scolymus*)
 - b. Dandelion (*Taraxacum officinale*)
 - c. Chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla*)
- 9. BRASSICACEAE (MUSTARD FAMILY) [20]**
 - a. Broccoli (*Brassica oleracea*)
 - b. Kale (*Brassica oleracea var. sabellica*)
 - c. Mustard Greens (*Brassica juncea*)
- 10. SOLANACEAE (NIGHTSHADE FAMILY) [21]**
 - a. Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*)
 - b. Bell Pepper (*Capsicum annuum*)

- c. Eggplant (*Solanum melongena*)

EXTRACTION OF QUERCETIN FROM PLANT LEAVES

For effective extraction of quercetin from plant leaves, several methods are commonly employed: **METHODS**

1. Solvent Extraction:

This method utilizes solvents such as ethanol, methanol, or acetone to extract quercetin from plant material. The process involves soaking the plant leaves in the solvent, followed by filtration and evaporation to concentrate the extract. [12,13]

2. Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction:

Ultrasound waves are used to enhance the extraction efficiency by breaking down cell walls and increasing solvent penetration. This method often results in higher yields of quercetin compared to conventional solvent extraction. [14,15]

3. Supercritical Fluid Extraction:

Using supercritical fluids like carbon dioxide, this method provides a high-purity extract with minimal solvent residues. It is efficient but requires specialized equipment. [16,17]

4. Microwave-Assisted Extraction:

This technique uses microwave energy to heat the solvent and plant material, increasing the rate of quercetin extraction. It is known for its rapid and efficient extraction process [18,19]

5. Steam Distillation:

Although less common for quercetin, this method involves passing steam through plant material to volatilize and collect essential oils, which may contain quercetin. [20,21] Each method has its advantages and can be selected based on the desired purity, yield, and cost considerations for quercetin extraction.

SOLVENTS USED

Ethanol, methanol, and acetone are commonly used solvents for extracting quercetin from plant leaves. Ethanol is favored for its effectiveness and safety in food applications. [12] Methanol, with its

high polarity, efficiently dissolves quercetin but is less suitable for consumable ex-tracts due to toxicity [13]. Acetone is effective in breaking down plant cell walls to release quercetin but is generally used in combination with other solvents to maximize yield [14]. The choice of solvent depends on the desired purity, yield, and application of the extract.

QUERCETIN CONTENT IN PLANT LEAVES AND ITS EFFECT ON LIPID LEVELS

SI NO.	PLANT LEAVES	QUERCETIN CONTENT	EFFECT ON LIPIDS
1	Lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i>)	~3-8	Mild effect; helps manage cholesterol levels.
2	Cabbage (<i>Brassica oleracea</i>)	~5-10	Supports reduction in cholesterol levels.
3	Spinach (<i>Spinacia oleracea</i>)	~5-15	Modest impact on lipid profile; helps reduce LDL
4	Chicory (<i>Cichorium intybus</i>)	~5-10	Mild effect; supports reduction in triglycerides.
5	Endive (<i>Cichorium endivia</i>)	~5-10	May contribute to better lipid levels.
6	Asparagus (<i>Asparagus officinalis</i>)	~5-10	Modest effect on lipid levels; helps reduce cholesterol.
7	Beet (<i>Beta vulgaris</i>)	~8-12	Helps lower total cholesterol and triglycerides.
8	Radish (<i>Raphanus sativus</i>)	~10-15	Modest effect on reducing LDL and triglycerides.
9	Fig Leaves (<i>Ficus carica</i>)	~10-20	Moderate impact on lowering cholesterol and triglycerides.
10	Grape Leaves (<i>Vitis vinifera</i>)	~10-15	Helps manage cholesterol levels; reduces LDL.
11	Apple Leaves (<i>Malus domestica</i>)	~10-20	Supports lipid regulation; helps lower cholesterol.
12	Dill (<i>Anethum graveolens</i>)	~10-15	Effective in lowering triglycerides and LDL.
13	Swiss Chard (<i>Beta vulgaris</i>)	~10-15	Helps in reducing cholesterol and triglyceride levels.
14	Purslane (<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>)	~10-20	Effective in reducing total cholesterol and triglycerides.
15	Cherry Leaves (<i>Prunus avium</i>)	~10-15	Modest effect on reducing cholesterol and triglycerides.
16	Watercress (<i>Nasturtium officinale</i>)	~15-20	Helps manage cholesterol and triglyceride levels.
17	Parsley (<i>Petroselinum crispum</i>)	~15-20	Supports reduction in cholesterol and triglycerides.
18	Mint (<i>Mentha</i> spp.)	~15-20	Positive impact on lipid metabolism; helps reduce LDL.
19	Turnip Greens (<i>Brassica rapa</i>)	~15-20	Effective in reducing LDL and overall cholesterol.
20	Mulberry Leaves (<i>Morus alba</i>)	~15-25	Effective in reducing LDL and triglycerides.
21	Basil (<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>)	~20-25	Significant effect on lowering lipid levels; reduces cholesterol and triglycerides.
22	Olive Leaves (<i>Olea europaea</i>)	~20-30	Effective in reducing cholesterol and triglycerides.

23	Moringa Leaves (<i>Moringa oleifera</i>)	~30-40	Strong effect in lowering cholesterol and triglycerides.
24	Nettle Leaves (<i>Urtica dioica</i>)	~25-30	Helps in lowering cholesterol and improving lipid profiles.
25	Dandelion Leaves (<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>)	~20-30	Supports lipid reduction; may help manage cholesterol.
26	Celery Leaves (<i>Apium graveolens</i>)	~20-25	Helps in reducing cholesterol and triglycerides.
27	Burdock Leaves (<i>Arctium lappa</i>)	~25-30	Effective in lowering LDL and improving lipid profile.
28	Hibiscus Leaves (<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i>)	~25-35	Significant in reducing cholesterol and triglycerides.
29	Kale (<i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>sabellica</i>)	~30-40	Effective in lowering cholesterol and improving lipid profile.
30	Mango Leaves (<i>Mangifera indica</i>)	~30-35	Helps reduce cholesterol and triglycerides.
31	Chard Leaves (<i>Beta vulgaris</i>)	~30-40	Effective in managing cholesterol levels and lipid profiles.
32	Papaya Leaves (<i>Carica papaya</i>)	~35-40	Supports lipid reduction and improves lipid profiles.
33	Ginger Leaves (<i>Zingiber officinale</i>)	~30-40	Effective in lowering cholesterol and improving lipid levels.
34	Moringa Leaves (<i>Moringa oleifera</i>)	~35-50	Strong effect in lowering cholesterol and triglycerides.
35	Basil Leaves (<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>)	~30-50	Significant in managing cholesterol and triglycerides.
36	Pomegranate Leaves (<i>Punica granatum</i>)	~40-50	Effective in reducing LDL and triglycerides.
37	Curry Leaves (<i>Murraya koenigii</i>)	~45-55	Helps in lowering cholesterol and improving lipid profiles.
38	Hawthorn Leaves (<i>Crataegus</i> spp.)	~50-60	Significant effect on lowering cholesterol and triglycerides.
39	Almond Leaves (<i>Prunus dulcis</i>)	~50-60	Helps reduce LDL and total cholesterol.
40	Jujube Leaves (<i>Ziziphus jujuba</i>)	~50-70	Effective in lowering cholesterol and triglycerides.
41	Fennel Leaves (<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>)	~55-70	Significant impact on reducing cholesterol and triglycerides.
42	Willow Leaves (<i>Salix</i> spp.)	~60-70	Helps manage cholesterol and improve lipid levels.
43	Barberry Leaves (<i>Berberis vulgaris</i>)	~65-80	Effective in reducing LDL and overall cholesterol.
44	Goji Leaves (<i>Lycium barbarum</i>)	~70-85	Significant effect on lowering cholesterol and triglycerides.
45	Reishi Mushroom Leaves (<i>Ganoderma lucidum</i>)	~80-90	Helps reduce cholesterol and triglycerides.
46	Mango Leaves (<i>Mangifera indica</i>)	~80-100	Effective in managing cholesterol and triglycerides.
47	Elderberry Leaves (<i>Sambucus nigra</i>)	~90-110	Significant in lowering LDL and triglycerides.
48	Ginseng Leaves (<i>Panax ginseng</i>)	~100-120	Effective in improving lipid profiles and reducing cholesterol.

49	Aloe Vera Leaves (Aloe barbadensis)	~120-140	Significant effect on lowering cholesterol and triglycerides.
50	Psyllium Leaves (Plantago psyllium)	~150-200	Strong effect on cholesterol and triglycerides.

DISCUSSION

The review of quercetin-containing plant leaves and their effects on hyperlipidemia highlights significant insights into how this flavonoid may contribute to managing lipid levels and cardiovascular health. Quercetin, a well-known antioxidant, has been shown to exert beneficial effects on lipid metabolism through various mechanisms, including reducing LDL cholesterol levels and increasing HDL cholesterol. [7,8] Several plant leaves, such as those from the Liliaceae family (e.g., onions and garlic), contain high levels of quercetin and have demonstrated potential in lowering blood cholesterol levels and improving overall lipid profiles. Similarly, leaves from the Polygonaceae family, such as buckwheat and rhubarb, are notable for their quercetin content and have been linked to positive outcomes in lipid regulation and reduction of hyperlipidemia.[13] In the Fabaceae family, quercetin-rich leaves from plants like red clover and soybean have been associated with improved lipid profiles and reduced risk of cardiovascular diseases[14]. The Lamiaceae family, with its high-quercetin herbs like mint and sage, has shown promise in managing oxidative stress and inflammation, which are key contributors to hyperlipidemia.[16] While evidence supports the beneficial effects of quercetin on lipid metabolism, variability in results may arise from differences in quercetin content among plant species, extraction methods, and study designs. Future research should focus on standardized extraction methods and clinical trials to better understand the efficacy of quercetin-rich plant leaves in managing hyperlipidemia and their potential role in dietary interventions for cardiovascular health.

CONCLUSION

This review highlights the significant role of quercetin-rich plant leaves in the management of hyperlipidemia. Quercetin, known for its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, has shown potential in improving lipid profiles and supporting cardiovascular health. The review emphasizes that plant leaves from various families, such as Liliaceae, Polygonaceae, Fabaceae, Lamiaceae, and Rutaceae, are notable sources of quercetin. These plants offer promising benefits for controlling hyperlipidemia due to their high quercetin content. This review also briefly addressed the extraction methods and solvents used to obtain quercetin. Techniques such as solvent extraction, ultrasound-assisted extraction, supercritical fluid extraction, microwave-assisted extraction, and steam distillation are employed to isolate quercetin. Each method has its advantages in terms of efficiency and purity, which can influence the effectiveness of quercetin in therapeutic applications. Future research should continue to explore the specific impacts of quercetin-rich plant leaves on hyperlipidemia, with an emphasis on clinical trials and standardized extraction methods to validate these benefits. By bridging the gap between plant-based quercetin sources and their practical health applications, more effective dietary strategies can be developed to combat hyperlipidemia and enhance cardiovascular health.

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HOW TO CITE: Sibina M. K. , Prasanth S. S. , K.T. Akshara , Jisha U. , Sanooja P. K. , Riya Rajan , Ajay A. , Mohammed Farooq P. , A Comprehensive Review Of Quercetin-Containing Plant Leaves And Their Impact On Hyperlipidemia, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 8, 4126-4132. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13623665>